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QUALITATIVE STUDY OF FIN FISH AND SHELL FISH FAUNA OF THANE CREEK AND ULHAS RIVER ESTUARY

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ABSTRACT : An attempt has been made to obtain the comparative finfish & Shellfish fauna qualitatively from the Thane creek and Ulhas river estuary during Nov. 2001 to Oct. 2002 dividing each of these two coastal water bodies into three zones (Riverine zone I, Middle zone II, Seaward zone III). Although the total no. of species found in the Thane creek was high (67 spp.) as compared to Ulhas river estuary (58 spp.), the upper zones (I & II) of the former and zone I of the later contain very low diversity of fish fauna. The salinity trend of zone -I of Thane Creek is fairly nearer to zone -II of Ulhas River Estuary but there is considerable difference in the fishery composition. It seems that various human activities like industrial effluents, domestic waste disposal, reclamation, sand dredging and eradication of mangrove flora have deteriorated these dynamic habitats causing decline in their fin fish & shell fish fauna during last two decades. It has been observed that the mudskippers, prawns have been completely eradicated from the entire stretch of the Thane creek due to heavy industrial & domestic waste disposal although there is fairly good mangrove vegetation along its west bank. In case of Ulhas river estuary, the sand dredging, occurring on its southern bank has forced the bottom dwellers like mudskippers, prawns & crabs to shift towards northern bank in zone II and III.

A fairly good variety of fishery at the mouth of Thane creek and Ulhas river estuary indicated that timely implementation of mitigation measures may revive the fishery of the two ecosystems.

Keywords: Qualitative Fish Fauna, Thane creek, Ulhas river estuary, anthropogenic activities.

INTRODUCTION

The coastal inward waters play important role as refuge to the fishes from marine as well as adjacent water bodies. Various fish and non-fish spp. visiting the inward waters like estuaries, lagoons, creeks and marshes in addition to the endemic species increase the diversity of their fauna. These habitats holding halophyte vegetation like mangroves and organic rich mudflats prove to be ideal for their feeding and breeding activities. The environments like creeks and estuaries along the coastal regions exhibit seasonal change in the species composition as different fin fish and shell fish species are attracted during the seasons to their feeding or breeding niche. Therefore these habitats overall hold rich fish faunal diversity.

The two dynamic environments, the Thane creek and Ulhas river estuary situated in the vicinity of the Mumbai-Thane complex, are the major water bodies supporting the local fisher folk for their livelihood from many decades. They are experiencing declined productivity and a miserable condition at present as these two aquatic habitats are heavily burdened by the industrial and urban activities, since long. Comparison of data with the earlier studies reveal that several species of prawns, crabs, bivalves, gastropods and fin fish which were caught in the upper reaches of these two environments (Mutsaddi, 1964, Qamrul, 1980; Tandel, 1984; Pejavar, 1984), are now a days vanished completely from the areas.

The Thane creek (Lat. 19° .00 to 19° .15 N; Long. 72° .55 to 73° .55) situated eastwards of Thane City is 26 km long opening at its southwest approach to Mumbai Harbour bay and is connected at its northern end to the Ulhas River Estuary by a narrow connection. The creek has basin about 2.5 m at high tide traversed with rocky floor intermittently. The slow tidal current encourage formation of mudflats. Mangroves are densely populated on the west bank of the creek. The creek receives treated and untreated domestic wastes and effluents from industries like chemical, petrochemical, fertilizers etc. situated throughout the Belapur belt on east bank (Athalye, 1988; Goldin, 2001).

Ulhas river (Lat. 18° .45' to 19° .00' N ; Long. 72° .45' to 73° .20' E).being very long and having big catchment area as it confluent with a number of tributaries (Qamrul, 1980); covering almost the Thane district measuring total of 122 km. in length, with an influence of the tidal water to about 40 km. upstream upto Dombivali - Kalyan stations forming an estuary ; meanders through Mumbra, Thane city, Kasheli, Kavani (Diva), Gaimukh, Ghodbunder and Bhayander before it joins the Arabian Sea at Vasai creek. The river annually collects about 2433.82 million cubic metres of water from Karjat, Kalyan and Murbad Talukas. It holds rich and diverse fish fauna since it not only carries the brackish waters in the lower reaches but also the fresh water in the upper reaches.

The rivers appear as the major sources of sediment for the beach deposits and sand on the Indian coast (Chandramohan *et al.*, 2001). The Ulhas river estuary is exploited since long for its sand resources along with fisheries.

The estuary is influenced considerably by industrial effluents from M.I.D.C., Bhiwandi (Qamrul, 1980) and domestic waste regularly added from the adjacent areas. Thus due to the decline in fisheries most of the fisher folk have turned down to sand extraction business being easily adoptable as they already have boats as a requirement for the sand extraction. However, the sand dredging affects the floor of channel of the estuary and disturbs the sedentary or bottom dwelling organisms. On the top of that the mangrove vegetation has been totally removed from the sand landing stations.

In the present paper aspects like important stress factors, fishing nets and qualitative fishery are recorded to show the zone wise extent of pollution.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

For the study three zones were imagined in each of the two environments the Thane Creek and Ulhas River Estuary as Zone I (Riverine end), Zone II (Middle region), Zone III (Seaward end) (Fig. 1).

Water and Sediment study

Monthly water and sediment samples were studied from four stations from each zone during period of Nov. 2001 to Oct. 2002 using Standard Methods (APHA, AWWA, WPCF, 1981) to assess important parameters and zone wise averages were calculated.

FISH FAUNA STUDY

Zone wise samples of the fishes were collected directly from the net, from Nov. 2001 to Oct. 2002 and carried to the laboratory in icebox for further investigation. Identification was performed using the keys given in

Fig. 1 : Map showing Ulhas river estuary and Thane Creek

'Fishes of India' (Day, 1889). Care was taken to ensure the collection from all possible type of the gears used along the estuary by the local fishermen viz. barrier net (Vana), hand net (Yeri), bag net (Bokshi & Dol), drift net (Disco jali) and hand picking in predominant fishing areas. The fishing intensity in most of the parts of these ecosystems fluctuates seasonally and even daily on an account of unattractive yield. Due to this reason the quantitative data was approximate and hence not considered for this presentation.

At each station the data on different types of fishing net used for different methods of fishing, polluting sources and sand dredging etc. was recorded through observation and interview with the fishermen.

Though the study was done at each station for convenience data has been consolidated zone wise.

Table 1 : Water and sediment parameters of Ulhas river estuary and Thane creek

Water Parameters	Ulhas River Estuary									Thane Creek										
	Zone 1			Zone 2			Zone 3			Total	Zone 1			Zone 2			Zone 3			Total
	Min	Max	Avg	Min	Max	Avg	Min	Max	Avg	Avg	Min	Max	Avg	Min	Max	Avg	Min	Max	Avg	Avg
Water Temperature °C	21.25	33.13	28.03	21	31.5	28.19	22.75	33.25	28.35	28.18	21.5	33.75	28.75	22.5	33.45	29.37	26.38	34.88	30.28	29.71
Suspended solids grm/l	0.16	0.96	0.555	0.15	2.375	1.249	0.205	6.15	3.865	1.89	0.43	3.385	1.911	0.6	13.5	2.414	0.535	3.17	1.551	1.958
Salinity ppt.	0.389	18.51	8.93	0.73	30.28	15.34	1.035	34.92	22.93	15.73	0.803	32.48	19.67	2.85	34.6	23.93	6.825	37.14	27.55	23.73
Dissolved oxygen mg/l	0.75	3.825	2.29	1.425	3.35	2.55	1.983	4.8	3.62	2.82	0.375	2.925	2.015	0.7	8.2	1.998	0.925	4	2.11	2.041
B.O.D. mg/l	5.375	24.43	16.25	2.225	13.48	8.341	0.55	8.45	5.083	9.892	9.75	42.75	24.67	2.125	24.13	13.04	1.9	20.05	10.79	16.17
PO ₄ -P mg/l	0.03	0.094	0.06	0.03	0.092	0.055	0.023	0.061	0.047	0.054	0.061	0.162	0.132	0.033	0.096	0.074	0.027	0.094	0.069	0.092
NO ₃ -N mg/l	0.292	2.521	1.491	0.905	3.533	1.89	0.189	2.275	1.616	1.666	0.471	1.458	1.022	0.145	2.099	0.853	0.145	1.383	0.983	0.953
SiO ₂ -Si mg/l	12.66	77.43	33.67	11.1	72.6	34.07	11.72	61.09	29.07	32.27	12.25	43.02	26.66	8.498	35.15	22.34	5.734	38.98	15.88	21.63
Sediment parameters																				
Organic C %	1.906	4.183	3.102	2.045	3.878	2.926	1.58	3.595	2.611	2.88	2.727	4.512	3.81	2.688	4.568	3.554	2.185	4.003	3.222	3.529
Carbon % Sand %	3.7	15	8.406	8.528	17.5	12.65	14.13	21.91	18.53	13.19	0.895	10	5.18	2.838	10	6.067	4.975	12.5	8.979	6.742
Silt %	48.75	74.1	59.69	30	55.52	41.52	30	69.68	48.88	49.36	62.5	82.23	76.34	63.36	81.07	69.88	60.57	75	65.53	70.59
Clay %	16.34	40	31.9	33.74	52.5	45.84	10.22	52.71	34.6	37.45	15	27.5	18.48	15.86	32.6	24.05	13.75	32.11	25.81	22.77

Table 2 : Types of disturbances observed in Ulhas river estuary and Thane creek.

No	Sand dredging activity	Ulhas River estuary			Thane creek		
		Z-I	Z-II	Z-III	Z-I	Z-II	Z-III
A							
1.	No. of boats engaged in sand excavation	11	83	8	-	-	-
2.	Sand landing stations	2	7	2	-	-	-
	Total A	13	90	10	-	-	-
No.	B Other anthropogenic activities						
1.	Major sewage & industrial effluent outlets	4	3	5	12	9	1
2.	Distruction of mangrove sites through solid waste dumping and reclamations.	3	4	3	2	2	1
		6	5	4	4	4	4
	Total B	13	12	12	18	15	6

Table 3 : Types of Fishing activities in Ulhas river estuary and Thane creek.

No	FISHING TYPE	Ulhas River estuary			Thane creek		
		Z-I	Z-II	Z-III	Z-I	Z-II	Z-III
1.	Mudskipper fishing	2	2	24	-	-	-
2.	Bag net (Dol/Bokshi)	-	20	71	-	-	11
3.	Barrier net (Vana)	2	15	12	1	4	35
4.	Driftnet (Disco jail)	-	2	-	1	45	250
5.	Dragnet (Yeri)	1	-	-	-	-	10
							(150)*
	Total	5	38	107	2	49	306
* The gear was used extensively for prawn fishing from March to May and August to October, when water temperature was high.							

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The important water parameters (Table 1) clearly indicate higher level of pollution in Thane creek as compared to Ulhas river estuary.

Thane creek had hypoxic dissolved oxygen (avg < 2.5 mg / l) through out the creek whereas Ulhas river estuary had hypoxia mainly in zone I. Both ecosystems have very high suspended solids and high nutrients, especially SiO₃-Si. Sediment parameters (Table 1) also indicate high organic carbon contents in the sediment of Ulhas river estuary and Thane creek (significantly higher in the later). In general significant pollution is observed in zone I of Ulhas river estuary and the entire stretch of Thane creek.

Table 2 shows different factors causing of pollution in Ulhas river estuary and Thane creek which include mainly sewage and industrial outlets, reclamation and destruction of mangroves through various activities like solid waste dumping or sand landing etc. In Thane creek zone I and II have more pollution causing factors than zone III whereas in Ulhas river estuary they are

almost the same in all the zones but they prove more damaging in zone I as it is narrower with lesser water mass. Ulhas river estuary has an additional stress in form of sand excavation activity which is high especially in zone II. The sand extraction and landing activities are concentrated on the south bank of the river (due to easy access to the city and the road transport). Previously mechanised dredgers were used which have been banned since 1995. Sand excavation however has kept the riverbed deep and has helped in retaining flushing characteristic of the estuary. Due to this siltation in zone II and III is less as compare to zone I (Table 1). It has however increased the suspended solids and also the silicates in Ulhas river estuary.

The above stress conditions have affected fishery and the effects are felt by the native fisherfolks. They avoid fishing in the area where fish is not available. Table 3 shows fishing gears / nets operated in each zone. The fishing activity in both ecosystems is maximum near the mouth, intermediate in the middle zone and very poor in the riverine zone I. This infact is logical even in an unpolluted creek or estuary. However the present number

Table 4 : Zone wise occurrence of the Fin fish fauna in the Ulhas river estuary Thane Creek

No	FIN-FISH FAUNA		ULHAS RIVER ESTUARY			THANE CREEK		
	SPECIES	FAMILY	Z-I	Z-II	Z-III	Z-I	Z-II	Z-III
1	<i>Boleophthalmus dussumieri</i>	Gobiidae	+	+	++++	-	-	+
2	<i>Boleophthalmus boddaerti</i>		-	+	+++	-	-	+
3	<i>Gobioides tenuis</i>		-	+	+	-	-	-
4	<i>Gobius giuris</i>		-	+++	+	-	-	++
5	<i>Gobius ocelatus</i>		-	-	++	-	-	+
6	<i>Tripauchen vagina</i>		-	++	+++	-	-	-
7	<i>Eleotris amboinensis</i>		-	-	-	-	-	+
8	<i>Sillago sihama</i>	Trachinidae	-	+	++	-	-	+++
9	<i>Kawala coval</i>	Clupeidae	-	+	+++	-	-	+++
10	<i>Trichiurus savala</i>		-	++	+++	-	-	+++
11	<i>Clupea sp.</i>		-	++	++++	-	-	++
12	<i>Pellona feligera</i>		-	++	+++	-	+	++
13	<i>Pellona elongata</i>		-	++	++	-	-	++
14	<i>Coilia Dussumieri</i>		-	+	+++	-	-	+++
15	<i>Chaetosus chacunda</i>		-	-	+++	-	++	++
16	<i>Chaetosus nasus</i>		-	+	++	+	+	+++
17	<i>Engraulis sp.</i>		-	++	+++	-	-	+
18	<i>Megalops cyprinoids</i>		++	+	+	-	-	++
19	<i>Etroplus maculatus</i>	Chromidae	-	++	++	-	-	++
20	<i>Chrysophrys datnia</i>	Sparidae	-	++	++	-	-	++
21	<i>Haplochilus lineatus</i>	Cyprinodontidae	-	++	++	-	-	-
22	<i>Mugil spigleri</i>	Mugilidae	+	-	+++	+	-	++
23	<i>Muugil Dussumieri</i>		-	++	-	+	-	++
24	<i>Batrachus grunniens</i>	Batrachidae	-	+++	+	-	-	+
25	<i>Lates calcarifer</i>	Percidae	+	+	+	-	+	++
26	<i>Therapon theraps</i>		-	+	+++	-	+	+++
27	<i>Therapon jarbua</i>		+	-	+++	-	+	+++
28	<i>Teuthis cramin</i>		-	++	-	-	-	++
29	<i>Oreochromis mossambicus</i>	Cichlidae	++	+++	++	-	+	+
30	<i>Mystus gulio</i>	Siluridae	++	+	++	++	+++	++
31	<i>Mystus sp.</i>		+	+	++	-	-	++
32	<i>Arius thalassinus</i>		+	-	+++	-	-	++
33	<i>Plotossus arab</i>		-	-	-	-	-	-
34	<i>Osteogentiosus militaris</i>		-	+	-	-	-	+
35	<i>Barbus pinnauratus</i>	Cyprinidae	-	++	-	-	-	++
36	<i>Scaena Dussumieri</i>	Sciaidae	-	-	++++	+	+	+++
37	<i>Scaena glaucus</i>		+	+	-	-	+	+++
38	<i>Otolithoides brunneus</i>		-	-	++	-	+	++
39	<i>Umbrina russellii</i>		-	+	-	-	-	++
40	<i>Tetrodon Fulvtilis</i>	Gymnodontes	-	+	++	-	-	+
41	<i>Tetrodon oblongus</i>		-	-	++	-	-	+
42	<i>Tetrodon stellatus</i>		-	-	-	-	-	+
43	<i>Tetrodon lunaris</i>		-	-	-	-	-	+
44	<i>Polynemus tetradactylus</i>	Polynemidae	-	-	+	-	-	+++
45	<i>Cynoglossus elongates</i>	Pleuronectidae	-	-	++	-	-	++
46	<i>Cynoglossus lingua</i>		-	+	+	-	-	++
47	<i>Congromuraena anago</i>	Muraenidae	-	-	++	-	-	+
48	<i>Harpodon nehereus</i>	Scopelidae	-	-	++	-	-	+
49	<i>Sciothagus argus</i>	Squamipinnes	-	-	+++	-	-	+
50	<i>Triachanthus brevirostris</i>	Sclerodermi	-	-	+	-	-	+
51	<i>Triachanthus strigilifer</i>		-	-	-	-	-	+
52	<i>Caranx sp.</i>	Carangiidae	-	-	-	-	-	++
53	<i>Equula rueonius</i>		-	++	++	-	-	++
54	<i>Equula splendens</i>		-	-	-	-	-	++
55	<i>Equula insidiatrix</i>		-	-	-	-	-	+
56	<i>Equula Dussumieri</i>		-	-	-	-	-	+
57	<i>Rastrelliger kanagurta</i>	Scombridae	-	-	-	-	-	++
58	<i>Cybbium guttatum</i>		-	-	-	-	-	+
59	<i>Echeneis neuerates</i>		-	-	-	-	-	+
60	<i>Stromateus argenteus</i>	Stromatidae	-	-	-	-	-	+
61	<i>Stromateus sinensis</i>		-	-	-	-	-	+
	Total no of spp.		10	34	41	5	11	55

Table 5 : Zone wise occurrence of shell fish in Ulhas river estuary and Thane creek.

Shell Fish Fauna		Ulhas river estuary			Thane creek			
No	SPECIES	FAMILY	Z-I	Z-II	Z-III	Z-I	Z-II	Z-III
1	<i>Parapenaëopsis sculptilis</i>	Penaeidae	-	+++	++	-	-	-
2	<i>Peneaus sp.</i>		-	+++	+++	-	+	+
3	<i>Metapenaëus monoceros</i>		-	+	++	-	-	++
4	<i>Metapenaëus sp</i>		-	-	++	-	-	-
5	<i>Penaëus indicus</i>		-	-	++	-	-	+
6	<i>Trachypenaëus sp.</i>		-	-	+	-	-	-
7	<i>Macrobrachium rosenbergii.</i>	Palaemonidae	-	++	+	-	-	-
8	<i>Acetus sp.</i>	Sergestidae	-	+	+	-	-	+
9	<i>Alpheus sp.</i>	-	-	-	+	+	-	++
10	<i>Cardium sp.</i>	-	-	-	++	-	-	++
11	<i>Paphia sp.</i>	-	-	++	+	-	-	-
12	<i>Katelysia</i>	-	-	-	++	-	-	-
13	<i>Portunus sanguinolentus</i>	-	-	-	++	-	-	+
14	<i>Charybdis sp.</i>	-	-	-	++	-	-	-
15	<i>Scylla serrata.</i>	-	++	++++	++	-	-	+
16	<i>Octopus sp</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
17	<i>Loligo sp..</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
Total No of spp.			3	9	15	1	6	12

Table 6 : Fish composition in Ulhas river estuary and Thane creek.

No	FISHING	Z-I	Z-II	Z-III	Total	Z-I	Z-II	Z-III	Total
1.	Fin fishery	10	34	41	43	5	11	55	55
2.	Shell fishery	3	9	15	15	1	6	12	12
	Total fishery	13	43	56	58	6	17	67	67
	Percentage	22	74	97	100	9	25	100	100

of the fishing nets is at least 1/8 th of the nets operated 15 year ago. The fishery yield of these ecosystems, is drastically reduced to such an extent that the fishermen are taking up other jobs for their living. Gokhale & Athalye (1995) have reported 67 % decrease in the fishery in zone I of Thane creek. In Ulhas river estuary very few nets are operated on the south bank due to sand excavation and sand landing activities concentrated on this bank.

Tables 4 & 5 show the types of fin and shell fishery respectively, obtained in each zone of Thane creek and Ulhas river estuary. In general there is more shell fishery variety in Ulhas river estuary as compared to Thane creek whereas types of fin fishery are more in Thane creek. However it is important to note that in Thane creek higher variety of fin & shell fishery types is obtained in the seaward region which is much broader than the mouth of Ulhas river estuary. In the fishery types of Ulhas river estuary, strictly marine types of fish are absent, hence the diversity of Ulhas river estuary is slightly lower than Thane creek. However in Ulhas river estuary 74 % of the fishery types penetrate upto zone II and 22 % upto zone I whereas in Thane creek only 25 % enter in zone II and 9 % in zone I (Table 6). Infact zone I of Thane

creek has physicochemical characteristics similar to zone II of Ulhas river estuary with which it is connected. However, it harbours very poor fishery as compared to zone II of Ulhas river estuary. Thus the qualitative fishery has got significantly affected by the pollution status of different zones of Thane creek and Ulhas river estuary. Apart from the above, following observations are noteworthy.

1. The *Trypauchen vagina*, *Katelysia spp.*, *Paphia spp.*, *Meretrix spp.*, *Cardium spp.*, mudskippers and prawns which were once abundant in Thane creek are absent presently in Zone I and Zone II. This is mainly due to (i) severe pollution and (ii) increased siltation which has made the substratum unfavourable for these species. Similar observation is also noted in zone I of Ulhas river estuary.

Infact absence of mudskipper can be used as an indicator of heavy pollution in creeks and estuaries.

2. Zone I and II of Thane creek have very heavy pollution by plastic bags which clogg the nets and fishing becomes impossible.

FISHERY OF THANE CREEK & ULHAS RIVER ESTUARY

Megalops spp.

(1) *Mugil Spigleri*
(2) *Mugil Dussumieri*

(1) *Pampus sinensis* (2) *Pampus argenteus* (3) *Sciaena dussumieri* (4) *Lates calcarifer*
(5) *Umbrina spp.* (6) *Sciaena spp.* (7) *Otolithus brunneus*

Gobioides spp.

Macrobrachium rosenbergii

3. A favourable observation to note is significantly good variety of fishery at the mouth of Thane creek. This fishery however is not able to penetrate in the creek. This indicates that if the pollution in the creek is checked, we will be able to revive the fishery of the creek. The same applies to zone I of Ulhas river estuary.

CONCLUSION

The observations in qualitative fishery of Thane creek and Ulhas river estuary have shown the areas and the extent of deterioration in the two ecosystems but at the same time they indicate the possibility of reveiving the systems if mitigation measures are implemented in time.

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